

The *Kerykeion* mint control linked coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes

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Since the preparation of a study published in 2019¹ on the typology and significance of the eastern imitative Athenian coinage previously attributed to Baktria,² and the associated mint control linked issues of Andragoras and Sophytes, a large hoard of these coins progressively entered the numismatic market over three years from late 2017.³ This has more than doubled the number of examples of the coinage previously known and yielded a number of new mint control types. These extend the typology established in the study and confirm the interpreted relative chronology of the eight series of emissions that comprise the coinage.⁴ This essay details two of the newly identified types bearing the *kerykeion* mint control and their significance within the established typological framework.

Parthia, Andragoras, c. 250-238 BC

AR Didrachm (7.98 g, 21 mm, 6h)	Struck c. 245-238 BC
	<p>OBV: Helmeted head of Athena r. REV: Owl stand r. head facing, AΘE to r., <i>kerykeion</i>, galley prow and grape vine branch to l. Ref: SNG ANS (9) -; Taylor Series 2, previously unknown with the <i>kerykeion</i> mint control, which defines a new Series 2 type 2.18. <i>Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 398.</i></p>

Prior to the identification of this didrachm, the *kerykeion* mint control was unknown on the imitative owls of Series 2, although it was identified on the last of the Athena/eagle drachms of Series 3 (types 3.6 and 3.7) as well as the issues of Sophytes (Series 7 and 8). The *kerykeion* is accompanied by a galley prow and grape vine branch, both of which are found on the immediately preceding coins in the sequence of Series 2 (types 2.13-2.17). The previously established progression of symbols indicates that this coin is the last of the Series 2 issues, the only type with three mint control

¹ Taylor (2019) based on a catalogue of coins compiled in mid-2017.

² Nicolet-Pierre and Amandry (1994); Bopearachchi (1996): Series 1; Bopearachchi (1998): 1-27; Van Alfen (2011): type III.F; Taylor (2019a): Series 1 and 2 re-attributed from 4th century BC Uncertain Baktria to mid-3rd century BC Andragoras, Satrap of Parthia.

³ *Roma Numismatics XIV* (21 September 2017), Catalogue: 106 which introduced the the Andragoras-Sophytes Group in numismatic trade, with a stated provenance ‘... a highly important group of coins which apparently came to light in the Oxus region in the 1960s, taken to Germany in 1975 when the owners emigrated there, and subsequently exported to the USA.’ Alternatively, Bordeaux and Bopearachchi (2018): slide 4 state that the coins of the group were part of a 2014 find of 600 coins in Afghanistan. All of the coins illustrated in this paper originate from the Andragoras-Sophytes Group. Their images are reproduced with thanks to Roma Numismatics <https://www.romanumismatics.com/>

⁴ The eight series are defined by differing iconography, epigraphy, fabric, and denominational composition. They progress from imitative Athenian owls (Series 1 and 2) to eagle reverse types (Series 3 -5), thence to cockerel reverse types (Series 7-8), punctuated briefly by an emission of tetradrachms bearing the name of Andragoras with the iconography of Tyche/Athena (Series 6); refer Taylor (2019) for a full exposition of each series and its characteristics.

symbols on the reverse. It extends the existing typology to become type 2.18. The *kerykeion* also serves to control link the imitative Athenian coinage of Series 2 with the Athena/eagle Series 3 types 3.6 and 3.7 (*kerykeion* plus grape vine branch mint controls), then to the coinage in the names of Andragoras (Series 6.6 newly identified below) and Sophytes (Series 7 and 8), each of which carry exclusively the *kerykeion* mint control on the reverse (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Another noteworthy feature is found on the obverse of this didrachm; the closed loop, or volute termination of the inner end of decorative visor on Athena’s helmet. This is a characteristic of the large denomination imitative Athenian coinage of Series 2, commencing with the tetradrachms of type 2.4. It is the standard depiction on the later series that involve the portrayal of an Attic helmet (Series 7 and 8).⁵ The volute termination of the decorative visor on the helmet is unknown on the prototype Athenian silver coinage until the second quarter of the 3rd century BC.⁶ This serves to place the mintage of the Series 2 imitative owls no earlier than the middle of the 3rd century BC.⁷ The appearance of this iconographic detail on Series 2 dispels the notion that these exceptionally detailed imitative owls date to 4th century BC Bactria.

Table 1. Mint control links between series.⁸

Mint Control	Series							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
No mint control	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Grape bunch	x	x						
MNA 	x	x						x
Vine branch 		x	x	x	x			
		x	x			x		
			x			x		
<i>Kerykeion</i>		x	x			x	x	x

Table 2. Relative Chronology based on development of mint controls.⁹

	4Drachm	2Drachm	Drachm	½Drachm	2Obol	1.5Obol	Obol
⇓	Series 1						
T	Series 2						
I	Series 2			Series 3			
M	Series 2		Series 3			Series 4	Series 5
E	Series 6	Series 3				Series 7	
⇓	Series 7				Series 7		
	Series 8						Series 8

⁵ Taylor (2019): 53-63.

⁶ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): Heterogeneous Groups B and C now attributed by Kroll (2013) to an Athenian civic mint of the second quarter (Group C) and third quarter (Group B) of the 3rd century BC.

⁷ Taylor (2020).

⁸ Updated from Taylor (2019): table 2.

⁹ Reproduced from Taylor (2019): table 3.

Parthia, Andragoras, c. 250-238 BC

AR Tetradrachm (17.04g, 25 mm, 6h)	Struck c. 245-238 BC.
	<p>OBV: Head of Tyche wearing mural crown, $\text{I}^{\text{A}}\text{P}$ (largely off-flan) behind, all within a dotted border.</p> <p>REV: ANΔPAΓOΠOY to r., Athena standing l. holding owl in r. hand, the other hand resting on a shield decorated with a Medusa head, grounded spear, point downward crossing diagonally behind, <i>kerykeion</i> in l. field, all within a dotted border.</p> <p>REF: Taylor Series 6, previously unknown with the <i>kerykeion</i> mint control, which defines a new Series 6 type 6.6.</p> <p><i>Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 327.</i></p>

The *kerykeion* mint control on this coin was previously unknown on the Tyche/Athena issues of Series 6 that carry the name of Andragoras on the reverse. This tetradrachm bears the $\text{I}^{\text{A}}\text{P}$ monogram, a primary mint control behind the neck of Tyche on the obverse.¹⁰ Although struck largely off-flan, this monogram is known from an obverse die matched example of Series 6 (type 6.3). It is also found on types 6.4 and 6.5, plus some of the drachms of Series 3 (type 3.5), as well as a variant form (Table 1) on the tetradrachms and didrachms of Series 2 (types 2.12-2.16). The identification of this coin, bearing a *kerykeion* on the reverse, extends the Series 6 typology to become type 6.6.

The presence of the *kerykeion* also serves to control link the Series 6 emission bearing the legend ANΔPAΓOΠOY (of Andragoras) with the succeeding emissions carrying the legend ΣOΦYTOY (of Sophytes). The latter consist of the Athena /cockerel (Series 7) and the Male Head/cockerel (Series 8) emissions, both of which bear an identical *kerykeion* in the left field of the reverse (Table 1 and Figure 1). The *kerykeion* on this coin supports the interpreted relative chronology (Table 2) presented in the previous study.¹¹ The last of the Andragoras emission (type 6.6) was struck contemporaneously with the last of the Athena/owl (Series 2, type 2.18 as detailed above) and Athena/eagle (Series 3, types 3.6-3.7) emissions, both of which bear the *kerykeion* accompanied other symbols (prow and/or vine branch) that were introduced earlier in the sequence.¹²

In conclusion, the identification of these two previously unknown varieties of Series 2 and Series 6, each bearing a *kerykeion*, strengthens the coherency of the interpretation¹³ of the control linked sequence of larger denomination emissions belonging to the period of Andragoras, the satrap of Parthia, who it appears was briefly succeeded by Sophytes in the closing stage of the Parni conquest of Parthia led by Arsaces I. These coins, and their control linked counterparts, serve

¹⁰ Taylor (2019): 63-64 for an elaboration of the hierarchy of mint control placement and the significance of an obverse mint control.

¹¹ Taylor (2019): 62-63 and table 3.

¹² Taylor (2019): 62-64 for a full exposition of the sequencing rationale based on the progressive development of mint controls and the evolution of the mint's control system using a multiplicity of mint controls variously on the obverse and reverse.

¹³ This illustrates the significance of sampling as noted by Taylor (2019): 64-65 who based on statistical analysis concluded that the then (mid-2107) available sample of the coinage suggested a low survival rate and that 'It also implies that our sample of the mint controls and associated links is potentially incomplete, a fact to bear in mind in the interpretation of the sequence typology.'

THE KERYKEION MINT CONTROL LINKED COINAGE OF ANDRAGORAS AND SOPHYTES

to define an event on which the sparse historical record is silent; the transfer of authority from Andragoras to Sophytes in a brief interlude before the complete conquest of Parthia by Arsaces.

Andragoras (Series 2.18 didrachm)

Andragoras (Series 3.7 drachm)

Andragoras (Series 6.6 tetradrachm)

Sophytes (Series 7.1 tetradrachm)

Sophytes (Series 8.3 tetradrachm)

Figure 1. *Kerykeion* control linked coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes.¹⁴

¹⁴ Top to bottom: Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 398; Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 335; Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 327; Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 364; Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 365.

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